

Fatigue modelling and fast testing methodologies to optimise part design and to boost lightweight materials deployment in chassis parts

Understanding the fatigue notch sensitivity of high-strength steels through fracture toughness

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DATE: 29th June 2023

Project objective

FATIGUE
4LIGHT

EU H2020 project
PID2019-106631GB-C41

FATIGUE
4LIGHT

Project objective - Key Messages

PROJECT MAIN OBJECTIVE

12-15% EV structural weight reduction
24-30% Lighter Chassis

Strategy to achieve the objective:

- ❑ materials solutions with high fatigue performance (AHSS, stainless steel, Al alloys and hybrid metal-FRP materials)
- ❑ the development of new computer modelling with high fatigue prediction accuracy
- ❑ new experimental methodologies that reduce the testing time for new materials
- ❑ Consider **affordability** and **sustainability** of the proposed solutions, supported by the application of **LCA** and **LCC** studies.
- ❑ Consider transferability of the solutions analysed to a **wide range** of **LDV** electrical vehicles (passenger's cars and LDCV), including PHEV and HEV, and also **HDV**.

Project Partners

POLITECNICO DI TORINO

Chassis parts requirements

Main drivers:

Elevated fatigue properties and good formability

Chassis parts requirements

Fatigue strength (R=0) vs UTS

Surface integrity

- Roughness
- Coatings
- Trimming / Punching

Fracture toughness vs YS

AIM: Study the applicability of fracture toughness to predict the fatigue notch sensitivity of AHSS

Advanced high strength steels for chassis parts

Material	t [mm]	σ_{ys} [MPa]	σ_{UTS} [MPa]	A ₈₀ [%]	Microstructure
HR DP600	4.3	439	622	21	Ferrite – Martensite
HR 800CP	3.4	778	835	17	Ferrite/Bainite matrix – Martensite/Austenite islands
HR 980CP	3.5	957	1034	13	Ferrite/Tempered Martensite matrix – Upper Bainite/Austenite islands

Fatigue characterisation

Hourglass specimens
Polished edge
(unnotched)

Hourglass specimens
Trimmed edge
(notched)

- 1: rollover
- 2: smooth zone
- 3: fracture zone
- 4: burr
- 5: fracture angle

HR DP600
 $Cl = 7\%$

HR CP800
 $Cl = 8.8\%$

HR CP980
 $Cl = 8.6\%$

Fatigue tests – Stiffness method

- Stress ratio $\rightarrow R = 0.1$
- Control mode $\rightarrow \sigma$
- DIC system $\rightarrow \Delta \epsilon$
- Load frequency $\rightarrow 30 \text{ Hz}$
- Block length $\rightarrow 6000 \text{ cycles}$

Strain measurements \rightarrow Damage monitoring

Fracture toughness tests – *Essential Work of Fracture (EWF)*

Double Edge Notched Tensile (DENT) specimens

Multiple specimens with different fatigue pre-cracked ligament lengths

Energy required to initiate a crack in a material

Fatigue results

Testing time: 2-3h per specimen

Steel grade	Edge condition	σ_f [MPa]	σ_{f-SM} [MPa]
HR DP600	Polished	502 ± 5	465 ± 10
	Trimmed, Cl = 7%	470 ± 5	454 ± 20
HR CP800 SF	Polished	622 ± 9	619 ± 16
	Trimmed, Cl = 8.8%	426 ± 19	449 ± 11
HR CP980 SF	Polished	643 ± 30	678 ± 14
	Trimmed, Cl = 8.6%	429 ± 11	464 ± 67

Fatigue results

Polished

Trimmed

$$k_f = \frac{\sigma_{f-Trimmed}}{\sigma_{f-Polished}}$$

Fatigue strength reduction factor

Damage tolerance

Fatigue & fracture toughness

$$k_f = \frac{\sigma_{f-Trimmed}}{\sigma_{f-Polished}}$$

Fatigue strength reduction factor

Damage tolerance

Fatigue & fracture toughness

Dugdale approach

$$\frac{r_c}{a} = \left(\sec \frac{\pi \sigma_f}{2 \sigma_{YS}} - 1 \right)$$

$$r_c/a < 0.1$$

Small-scale yielding conditions are not fulfilled

Elastic-plastic fracture mechanics
Cyclic J-Integral \approx *EFW*

Steel grade	r_c / a
HR DP600	0.3
HR CP800 SF	0.1
HR CP980 SF	0.1

Fatigue resistance (R=-1) & fracture toughness

*Parareda et al. 2023 *Metals*, 13(6), 1117

<https://www.mdpi.com/2341696>

LCA grade 1000 CAE

HR CP800SF

JJ Lower Control Arm
Not in production yet

ASM weight, 3.12kg
Shell 1.80kg, 3.5mm

HR CP980SF

F4L Lower Control Arm

System level CAE assessment to identify weight improvement

- Misuse
- Fatigue (F4L material characterization and welding characterization is available)

Shell expected weight reduction 10-20%

F4L will proto 3.5mm thk grade 1000LCA → dedicated CAE component level to be used to correlate:

- Hard Cut edge fatigue test → parental material correlation
- Welding fatigue test (this test will be used to assess the improvement of shoot-peening on the welding)
- Longitudinal component misuse

LCA grade 1000 CAE: System Level Assessment → Fatigue

HR CP800SF 3.5 mm Lower Control Arm

Fatigue

	Geometry		Attitude Chart	Max Weight			Actual weights (stdC)			Tire
	Front	Rear		Front [kg]	Rear [kg]	Total [kg]	Front [kg]	Rear [kg]	Total [kg]	
JJ BEV	Rev7	Rev4 (iso356)	Rev03	1020	990	2010	1020	990	2010	215/45 R18

Setup: JJ EMEA BEV 370km F.Opt	
Front suspension	
Spring [mm/kg x kg]	0.304 x 428.0
Shock Absorber	Damper minimum
Stabilizer bar [mm]	∅25
Rear suspension	
Spring [mm/kg x kg]	0.247 x 338.0 <small>(modified to reach suspension flex. target)*</small>
Shock Absorber	Damper minimum
Engine	JJ BEV

Signal Names: JJ-20190516-BEV_370km_f125_Min-TbH-maxAmm-R18*.asc
 *: Attitude chart calculated considering 330 twistbeam geometry, while load calculation considers 356 geometry.

R50C50 → Target 200%

R50C50 → Target 200%

LCA grade 1000 CAE: System Level Assessment → Misuse

HR CP800SF 3.5 mm Lower Control Arm Misuse

	limit	Displacements [mm]	Load [N]	
CEDIMENTO VERTICALE Collapse Vertical (on one wheel - left)	F	elastic limit	80 mm	
		collapse limit	@ WC in Z	
		shock limits	direction	
	R	elastic limit	80 mm	
		collapse limit	@ WC in Z	
		shock limits	direction	
CEDIMENTO LONGITUDINALE direzione FRENATA Collapse Longitudinal (bracking) (on one wheel - left)	F	elastic limit	120 mm	
		collapse limit	@ WC in X	
		shock limits	Xdirection	
	R	elastic limit	120 mm	
		collapse limit	@ WC in X	
		shock limits	Xdirection	
CEDIMENTO LONGITUDINALE direzione FRENATA in retromarcia Collapse Longitudinal (bracking during reverse) (on one wheel - left)	R	elastic limit	100 mm	
		collapse limit	@ WC in X	
		shock limits	direction	
	COLLASSO LATERALE - BALCONATA CERCHIO INFERIORE (BCI) Collapse Lateral (lower rim) (on one wheel - left)	F	elastic limit	100 mm
			collapse limit	@ Lower rim in Y direction
			shock limits	direction
R		elastic limit	100 mm	
		collapse limit	@ Lower rim in Y direction	
		shock limits	direction	
COLLASSO LATERALE - BALCONATA CERCHIO INFERIORE (BCI) Collapse Lateral (upper rim) (on one wheel - left)	F	elastic limit	100 mm	
		collapse limit	@ Lower rim in Y direction	
		shock limits	direction	
	R	elastic limit	100 mm	
		collapse limit	@ Lower rim in Y direction	
		shock limits	direction	

Q= max GVM = 2010 kg
 S= MAX axle load FRONT = 1020 kg
 S= MAX axle load REAR = 990 kg
 Wheel Rim = 18 "
 Rim Misuse distance = 243.6 mm

LCA COLLAPSE
PEEQ_{MAX} = 14.5% > ε_f

LCA grade 1000 CAE: Component Level Assessment → Fatigue

HR CP980SF 3.5mm → hard cut edge fatigue

Edge failure!!!

LCA grade 1000 CAE: Component Level Assessment → Fatigue

HR CP980SF 3.5mm → Welding fatigue

Lower Control Arm + bushings (same characteristics of Misuse model)

	Force [N]		Cycles per Block	Blocks
	From	To		
Level 1	-6000	9000	1	50
Level 2	-6000	7000	1	
Level 3	-3000	9000	500	
Level 4	-5000	5000	800	

LEVEL 1: -8000/12000N
2500 cycles

Bench Test

Normal Welding

Shot Peened Welding

LCA grade 1000 CAE: Component Level Assessment → Misuse

HR CP980SF 3.5mm → Longitudinal misuse

System Results

Component Results

The deformation shape is different.

LCA Grade 1000: proto Manufacturing

Tiberina stamping process assessment

HR CP800SF

TIBERINA

Project Name: FIAT 516-364-966

Documentation
SHEET METAL FORMING
SIMULATION

HR CP980SF

TIBERINA

Project Name: FIAT 516 JJ

Documentation
SHEET METAL FORMING
SIMULATION

LCA Grade 1000: Proto Status

LCA Grade 1000: Proto Bench Test

No.	Scheme	Test Code	Test @ component	Samples	Signal	Target										
1	Load in Y Block Z 	F4L-01 HR CP980SF	Fatigue parental material (free border)	3	Sinusoidal +/-7500N 6hz	8900 cycles no failure Test to failure or stop at 13350										
2	Load in X Block Z 	F4L-02 HR CP980SF	Fatigue welding	3	Sinusoidal -8000N/+12000N 1.5hz	5000 cycles no failure Test to failure or stop at 7500										
3	Load in X Block Z 	F4L-03 HR CP980SF (welding with shot peening)	Fatigue welding	3	Sinusoidal -8000N/+12000N 1.5hz	5000 cycles no failure Test to failure or stop at 7500										
4	Disp 80mm in X Keep Pt5 Z 	F4L-04 HR CP980SF	Misuse Collapse	3	X=80mm (0.5mm/s) @pt5	<table border="1"> <thead> <tr> <th colspan="2"></th> <th>Fx [N]</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td rowspan="3">Longitudinal</td> <td>Elastic Limit</td> <td>19242</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Collapse Limit</td> <td>21252</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Shock Limit</td> <td>23262</td> </tr> </tbody> </table>			Fx [N]	Longitudinal	Elastic Limit	19242	Collapse Limit	21252	Shock Limit	23262
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THANK YOU!
